

BROMINATION OF COMPOUNDS CONTAINING TWO AROMATIC NUCLEI.
PART XVII. BROMINATION OF SOME ARYLAMIDES OF 2-HYDROXY-
4-METHYLBENZOIC ACID (*m*-CRESOTIC ACID)

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Bromination of anilide, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-toluidides, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-nitroanilides, *o*-, *p*-anisidides, *p*-phenetidide and β -naphthylamide has been carried out in presence of acetic acid and with liquid bromine. The constitutions of the bromo derivatives have been arrived at by their hydrolysis and identifying the acidic and basic components obtained.

Jadhav and Aslam (this *Journal*, 1947, 25, 201) brominated the aryl esters of *m*-cresotic acid and observed that bromine entered the acidic part only in presence of the solvent. It was with liquid bromine only that bromine was found to enter both the nuclei.

The present work was taken up with a view to studying the effect of the basic group like arylamino in place of the phenolic group towards bromination. It has been found that whenever mono-bromo derivatives are formed, bromine is found to enter the acidic part, which shows that the acidic part is more reactive than the basic one.

Whenever a dibromo derivative is formed, either with more solution or with liquid bromine, the latter is found to enter the basic part also except in the case of *m*- and *p*-nitroanilides, where it is found to enter the acidic part only.

With liquid bromine, however, higher bromo derivatives are obtained with bromine in both the nuclei.

The constitutions of the bromo derivatives have been arrived at by hydrolysing them with alkali or 80% sulphuric acid and identifying the basic and acidic components.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromination in Acetic Acid Medium.—This was carried out in boiling solution in the same way as was done in the case of arylamides of the *o*-cresotic acid in Part XVI (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 143) except in the case of anilide, *o*-nitroanilide and *p*-anisidide, where the addition was done at 70°-80°. Bromo derivatives are described in Table I.

Bromination with Liquid Bromine.—This was carried out at room temperature in the same way as in the case of the arylamides of *o*-cresotic acid (*loc. cit.*), except in the case of *o*-nitroanilide and *p*-anisidide, where the reaction mixture was boiled on a boiling water-bath for 4 hours and then left at room temperature. The bromo derivatives are described in Table II.

Hydrolysis.—(a) The bromo derivatives marked with an asterisk were hydrolysed with NaOH solution in the same way as described in the case of *o*-cresotic acid derivatives (*loc. cit.*) except in the case of *m*-toluidide and *o*- and *m*-nitroanilides, where benzene was used for extracting the base. The free base was identified by mixed melting point in the case of compounds marked † and through their acetyl derivatives in the case of compounds marked with ‡.

TABLE I

B denotes 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-benz- and B-5-B-, 2 hydroxy-4-methyl-5-bromo-benz-.

Arylamide.	Acetic Br ₂ acid. soln.	Bromo derivative.	Cryst. from.	Cryst. shape.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Bromine. Found.	% Bromine. Calc.	Hydrolysed for
B-anilide.	30 c.c.	B-5-B-anilide.**†	Dil. alcohol.	White needles	1.5 g.	211-12°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr	21.2	21.1	9 hrs.
B-o-toluidide.	30	B-5-B-o-toluidide.**†	Do	Do	1.5	158-59°	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ NBr	24.8	25.0	9
B-anilide.	30	B-5-B-4'-bromoanilide.**†	Do	White plates	1.5	198-99°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NBr ₂	41.7	41.6	6
B-m-toluidide.	40	B-5-B-4'-bromo-m-toluidide.**†	Do	White needles	1.5	232-33°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	39.8	40.1	14
B-p-toluidide.	30	B-5-B-p-toluidide.**†	Do	Do	1.5	245-46°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr	25.1	25	10
B-p-toluidide.	30	B-3:5-di-B-2'-bromo-p-toluidide.**†	Do	Do	2.0	194-95°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	50.4	50.1	8
B-o-nitroanilide.	50	B-5-B-o-nitroanilide.**†	Do	Yellow needles	1.5	173-74°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br	28.7	28.8	10
B-m-nitroanilide	80	B-5-B-m-nitroanilide.**†	Do	White needles	1.5	244-45°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br	22.6	22.8	8
B-p-nitroanilide	140	B-3:5-di-B-p-nitroanilide.**†	Acetic acid	Brown needles	1.3	241-42°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	37.0	37.2	6
B-o-aminiside	30	B-5:3-di-B-5'-bromo-o-aminiside.**†	Do	White needles	1.7	208-209°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	48.6	48.6	8
B-p-aminiside.	30	B-5-B-p-aminiside.**†	Dil. alcohol	Do	1.7	201-202°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr	23.6	23.8	6
B-p-aminiside.	30	B-5-B-3'-bromo-p-aminiside.**†	Do	Do	1.6	159-60°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	38.4	38.6	6
B-p-phenetidine.	25	B-5-B-p-phenetidine.**†	Dil. acetic acid.	Do	1.5	194-95°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ NBr	23.0	22.9	7
B-β-naphthylamide.	80	B-5-B-1'-bromo-β-naphthylamide.**†	Do	Do	1.7	229-30°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	36.7	36.8	6

TABLE II

B denotes 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-benz- and B-3:5-diB-denotes 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3:5-dibromo-benz-.

Arylamide.	Vol. of bromine.	Bromo derivative.	Cryst. from.	Shape of cryst.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Bromine. Found.	% Bromine. Calc.	Time of hydrolysis.
B-anilide.	3 c.c.	B-3:5-diB-2':4'-dibromo-anilide.**†	Acetic acid.	White needles	1.8 g.	215-16°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ NBr ₄	58.8	58.9	14 hrs.
B-o-toluidide.	3	B-3:5-diB-4'-bromo-o-toluidide.**†	Do	Do	1.7	210-11°	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ NBr ₂	50.1	50.2	8
B-m-toluidide.	3	B-3:5-diB-4':6'-dibromo-m-toluidide.**†	Do	Do	1.5	186-87°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ NBr ₄	57.7	57.4	15
B-o-nitroanilide.	3	B-3:5-diB-2'-nitro-4'-bromo-anilide.**†	Do	Yellow plates	2.0	192-93°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	47.0	47.2	15
B-m-nitroanilide	3	B-3:5-diB-m-nitroanilide.**†	Dil. acetic acid.	White needles	2.0	250-51°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	37.4	37.4	12
B-p-nitroanilide	3	B-3:5-diB-2'-bromo-4'-nitroanilide.**†	Acetic acid.	Dark brown needles	1.5	226-27°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	47.3	47.2	7
B-p-aminiside.	3	B-3:5-diB-3':6'-dibromo-p-aminiside.**†	Do	White needles	1.5	231-32°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ NBr ₄	55.7	55.8	7
B-β-naphthylamide	3	B-3:5-diB-1':5'-dibromo-β-naphthylamide.**†	Do	Do	1.8	265-66°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₄	54.0	53.9	8

The acidic component obtained from the alkaline filtrate on acidification was identified by mixed melting point with an authentic specimen. The bromo derivatives marked (**) were hydrolysed with 80% H_2SO_4 and worked out in the same way as was done in the case of some bromo derivatives of *o*-cresotic acid (*loc. cit.*).

The bromo-acid was identified through mixed melting point with a genuine specimen, and the base was identified by mixed melting point in the case of compounds marked (‡) and through their acetyl derivatives in the case of compounds marked †.

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